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EFFECTIVENESS OF DESIGN-BASED LEARNING IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT. Design-based learning (DBL) projects are open-ended. Team students work in hands-on and authentic tasks. The coaching role of the teacher providing formative individual feedback to the student teams becomes relevant to enhance the learning process. The effectiveness of these characteristics have not been fully explored in the context of engineering education and it is yet unknown which activities support students' preparation for such a practice in engineering educational. Our literature review consisted of an analysis of 50 empirical articles focusing on design tasks. Next, we have conducted a survey at engineering departments which implement design-based learning. The aim was to study what the teachers' and students' perceptions are about design characteristics. Results show differences in the perceptions of the teachers and students regarding the role of the teacher. It indicates that the role of the teacher and the practices around design-based learning projects are more traditional in some departments than in others.

Keywords: open-ended experiential projects, design-based learning, engineering education

INTRODUCTION

Design-based learning (DBL) is a learning approach which embarks students in engineering design (Mehalik and Schunn, 2006). The focus of design-based learning lies in the design of artefacts, systems and solutions (Wijnen, 2000). As an active learning method, design-based learning employs the pedagogical insights of problem-based learning (PBL). However, the characteristics of effective learning environments for design-based learning and the educational activities supporting students' preparation for such a practice have been hardly investigated in engineering education contexts. Our research question was to identify the perceptions of both teachers and students about design-based learning characteristics. We look more specifically into the characteristics of the projects, the role of the teacher, the assessment, the social context and the design elements in which design takes place. These

five dimensions are critical influencing factors in design-based learning as design tasks take place in projects.

The following sections address briefly the theoretical foundations, overview of the preliminary results of both the literature review and the quick scan. We conclude with some considerations on design-based learning in engineering design education.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

We present hereby the theoretical considerations of the five dimensions in which we focus on in this study, e.g. the design project characteristics, the role of the teacher, the assessment methods, the social context and the design elements. These five dimensions together are critical to and may influence effectively the learning environment in design-based learning.

THE FEATURES OF DESIGN-BASED LEARNING PROJECTS

Our first theoretical consideration is based on the intrinsic inquiring nature of engineering practices which lies in proposing solutions to users' and industry problems. One of our premises is that 'design' is an activity which concentrates on the learning that takes place during design projects. This design process implies acquiring gradually about *the nature of the design problem and the best routes to take towards a design solutions* (Lawson & Dorst, 2009, p. 34). Each step of the design process opens up a new experiential and discovery situation to propose solutions to ill-define multidisciplinary design problems (Savin-Baden, 2000, Hmelo-Silver, 2004, Lawson & Dorst, 2010). In the professional practices, engineers try out a broad range of strategies to look at the problem while experimenting with the solutions and the results to meet the needs of the society and the stakeholders.

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER

The teacher, as a tutor or instructor, has had a prominent role in the literature on problem-based learning in coaching students (Moust and Schmidt, 1994, Schmidt *et al.*, 1995, Hmelo-Silver, 2004, Moust *et al.*, 2005). The form coaching takes in supporting students both to become self-directed learners and to engage them in design tasks. The art of creating balance between teaching and learning, consequently, lies in shaping coaching and alternating scaffolding strategies such as guiding questions or assignments, to activate students in thinking activities, and gradually fading away when students have reached a level of thinking process (Vermunt and Verloop, 1999).

THE ASSESSMENT METHOD

There are some evidences referring to formative feedback which, as an assessment tool, becomes a feasible vehicle to increase motivation and ultimately, to support achievement also in individual learning (Black and Wiliam, 1998). The effects of formative assessment have been extensively explored in engineering education (Black and Wiliam, 1998), although it is still unknown what features are essential in design-based learning.

THE SOCIAL AND LEARNING CONTEXT

Drawing on empirical studies on new learning environments (Dinsmore *et al.*, 2008, Gijbels *et al.*, 2006), and on the characteristics of the multidimensional nature of learning, e.g. proper alignment of learner characteristics, teachers' knowledge, pedagogical practices and classroom resources and materials (Apedoe *et al.*, 2008, Gijbels *et al.* 2006, den Brok, 2010), students work actively communicating and reflecting with their peers (Hmelo-Silver *et al.*, 2007, Bolhuis, 2003), within real-life' settings constitute the backbone of educational effectiveness of learning environments.

THE DESIGN ELEMENTS

Given the fact that engineering design education is akin but not the same as the professional engineering design practice we adopt the classification on design steps that are reported to (potentially) constitute good design (Mehalik and Schunn, 2006). This classification builds upon the professional engineering design tasks undertaken in the real-life working places. DBL projects include design elements relevant for the student expertise required for particular design activities.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

We have explored the following questions:

1. *What are the specific characteristics of design projects that stimulate effective learning in design projects?*
2. *What are the perceptions of the teachers and the students on the design-based learning projects in Industrial Design, Architectural Building and Planning, Mechanical Engineering and Electrical Engineering departments at the Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e)?*

LITERATURE REVIEW

To find out the answers to our research questions on effectiveness in design-based learning, we have searched fifty empirical studies in the context of engineering education. The selection of the studies has been previously made to serve the purpose of another research study to identify the characteristics of what 'good design' is in engineering education.¹The result is a classification of engineering design elements specific to the domain, level of expertise (undergraduate or graduate), and authenticity of practices (artificial vs. authentic) (Gómez Puente *et al.*, 2011).

In order to characterize what good education is in engineering education we have screened once more the 50 empirical articles previously used to analyse good design elements. The data from the review of empirical studies illustrate effective educational aspects in design projects, and more specifically, on how the four dimensions (project characteristics, teacher's role, assessment methods, social context) are applied in projects.

SURVEY

To know the perceptions of the teachers and students about the characteristics of these projects in the context of the engineering programs, we have carried out a quick scan in four departments, Industrial Design, Architecture Building and Planning, Mechanical Engineering, and Electrical Engineering at Eindhoven University of Technology. The quick scan consisted of a questionnaire of forty questions including

¹ Articles refer to educational approaches in design schemes (e.g. problem/project based learning) which have been published in international journals indexed in the ISI Web of Science, the Education Resources Information Centre (ERIC) databases as well as a list of accepted journals of the Interuniversity Centre for Educational Research (ICO).

items from the five dimensions, e.g. project characteristics, teachers' role, assessment, social context, and the design elements on good design.

FINDINGS OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW

In the following sections, we provide an overview of the findings of the four dimensions.

PROJECTS' FEATURES

Table 1 provides an overview of the findings on the four dimensions.

From literature we found that design tasks are often framed in solving loosely formulated situations in an iterative process conducted in open-ended and hands-on design assignments (McMartin *et al.* 2000, Roberts, 2001, Hirsch *et al.* 2001, Denayer *et al.* 2003, Wood *et al.* 2005, Mese, 2006, Maase, 2008, Nonclercq *et al.* 2010, Linge *et al.*, 2006, Massey *et al.* 2006, Lee *et al.*, 2010), but also in authentic learning environments (Macías-Guarasa *et al.*, 2006, Mckenna *et al.*, 2006).

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER

In the literature, the coaching role of the teacher is associated with supervising acquisition of process competencies and guiding students in knowledge building and application is not fully delimited. Formative feedback focuses on three levels, e.g. task, process, but also on the self. The experiences of Cheville *et al.* (2005) Maase (2008) and Jacobson *et al.* (2006), show that the use of on-line quizzes prepare students as enter in class but help both teachers and students to monitor the process. Commonly, asking questions during different project implementation phases are employed to guide learners through the more complex parts of the design such as the process of scoping the problem, and inquiry and troubleshooting (Chang *et al.* 2008). In guiding students, the teacher, as a coach or as a facilitator, makes use of instructional scaffolding methods (e.g. worksheets with questions, use of a solution

plan to learn steps required in that solution process, or description of problem statement). These scaffolding methods are meant to serve as stepping stones for the student towards procedures to learning to learn.

ASSESSMENT

Design-based learning projects identified in the empirical studies suggest that individual formative assessment is a successful tool to monitor progress (Cheville *et al.*, 2005, Shyr, 2009, and Lee *et al.* 2010). Some of these methods include oral questioning, weekly presentations of individual reports in which students show the lab results and their understanding of exercises, or formative quizzes and a final examination. In the same line, Nooshabadi and Garside (2006), and Chang *et al.* (2008) emphasize that on-line weekly quizzes become a flexible assessment method by which the material presented in lectures and lab during the week can be easily tested.

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOCIAL CONTEXT

In effective design-based learning projects we found that projects resemble professional practices of the engineering community working in engineering teams. Communication, both oral and written becomes an essential component of the daily working flow as professionals exchange ideas, discuss multidisciplinary solutions and come to terms to make decisions. Communication takes place also with other stakeholders such as customers and users bodies (Massey *et al.* (2006), Behrens *et al.* (2010), Shyr, (2009). Communication implies active participation of students with their peers.

DESIGN ELEMENTS

The design elements encountered in design-based learning projects in the literature resemble design elements included in practices in real-life contexts. All projects analyzed include a representation of the design elements.

Project's features	Methods	Source
Open-ended Hands-on Authentic Multidisciplinary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No unique solution is given; search alternatives: • No specifications are given • Realistic scenarios: industry is involved in projects • Experimental character of projects • Integration of disciplines in projects and team teaching from different expertise 	Denayer et al. (2003) Macias-Guarasa et al. (2006) Linge & Parsons (2006) Massey et al. (2006) Nonclercq et al. (2010). Jacobson et al (2006) Mckenna et al. (2006) Wood et al., (2005) Lee et al., (2010)
Teachers' role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faculty (teachers) act as consultants • Coaching on tasks: technical designs • Coaching on process and self-development 	Denayer et al. (2003) Maase (2008) Massey et al. (2006)
Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formative assessment on individual contribution in team projects 	Nooshabadi & Garside (2006) Maase (2008) Shyr (2009) Lee, et al. (2010)
Social context: Group process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link with companies: industry gives feedback in presentations of prototypes or products • Collaborative and peer-to-peer learning 	Shyr (2009) Nooshabadi & Garside (2006) Massey et al. (2006) Maase (2008) Cheville et al. (2005) Denayer et al. (2003) Linge & Parsons (2006) Nonclercq et al. (2010) Mckenna et al. (2006)
Design elements	Explore problem representation; Use interactive/iterative design methodology; Search the space (explore alternatives); Use functional decomposition; Explore graphic representation; Redefine constraints; Explore scope of constraints; Validate assumptions and constraints; Examine existing designs; Explore user perspective; Build normative model; Explore engineering facts; Explore issues of measurement; Conduct failure analysis; Encourage reflection on process	Examples of articles in which we encountered a number of design elements Shyr (2009) Denayer et al. (2003) Nooshabadi & Garside (2006) Wood et al., (2005) Massey et al. (2006) Jacobson et al (2006) Maase (2008) Cheville et al. (2005) Denayer et al. (2003) Linge & Parsons (2006) Nonclercq et al. (2010) Mckenna et al. (2006)

Table 1 Classification of various methods of project characteristics which have shown effective learning

RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

The means scores of teachers' and students' perceptions on the five DBL characteristics results indicates that there are significant differences in the perceptions of teachers (3.9) and students (3.1) with respect to the

variable the teacher's role. Teachers' and students' perceptions are similar, (teachers' mean average 3.7, and students' mean average 3.4) with regards to the variables project characteristics, social context, assessment, and design elements.

		Project charact.	Social context	Teacher	Assessment	Design elements
Student	Mean	3,3	3,3	3,1	3,6	3,4
	Std. deviation	,46	,72	,69	,55	,44
Teacher/tutor	Mean	3,7	3,5	3,9	3,9	3,8
	Std. deviation	,64	,59	,54	,52	,49

Table 2. Means and standard deviations of teachers/tutors and students on the five dimensions of the instrument

CONCLUSIONS

We have reviewed a number of empirical studies with a focus on searching the effective characteristics of the five dimensions, e.g. project characteristics, teacher's role, assessment, social context and design elements. In addition, we have carried out a survey study in four engineering departments (Industrial Design, Architecture Building and Planning, Mechanical Engineering, Electrical Engineering) to explore the perceptions of the teachers and the students.

Regarding the characteristics of design-based learning projects, effective design tasks are embedded in open-ended, hands-on, experiential and authentic learning environments in which students create solutions and make design resembling the nature of multidisciplinary engineering community of professionals. The teachers' role in design projects focuses mainly in providing coaching to students by providing feedback on task, process and self. In doing so, the teachers may use different techniques, e.g. guiding questions, worksheets, in balancing the freedom for students to guide own process while still monitoring the learning process closely. Concerning the effectiveness of assessment instruments, evidences from empirical experiences show that individual learning in project team can be better stimulated by formative feedback by the teacher on the one hand, but also by peer-to-peer activities, self-assessment and reflection on own progress, on the other. Pertaining to the social context, an optimal implementation of design projects includes both group and peer collaboration in which students work in teams in iterative design assignments, perform professional roles and use the engineering community language. Finally, the design elements are domain-specific and are to emulate professional engineering practices.

The perceptions of the teachers and students differ in relation to the variable on the role of the teacher. Our initial interpretation of this result is that the role of the teacher and the practices around design-based learning projects are more traditional in some departments than in others. The coaching role of the teacher in these practices may focus more on technical aspects than in process-oriented and self-development, on the one hand. On the other, individual formative feedback may not be part of the common practices.

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